

SCIENTIFIC-THEORETICAL ISSUES AND PEDAGOGICAL CONDITIONS OF FORMING SPEECH CULTURE IN PRIMARY STUDENTS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20554044>

Abstract. *This article studies the scientific theories and pedagogical conditions for the formation of speech culture in primary school students. The methodology for developing oral and written speech of students based on modern educational requirements is analyzed. During the study, the effectiveness of interactive methods and digital technologies in developing speech was proven through experimental work. The article also analyzes the definition of the concept of speech, the history of its emergence, and the views of Eastern scholars on the need to develop speech.*

Keywords: *speech, culture, primary school, methodology, native language, student, teacher, modern approach, pedagogy, effectiveness.*

INTRODUCTION. The main goal of the modern education system is to educate a comprehensively developed, independent and creatively thinking individual. The foundation of personal development is laid in the primary grades. The formation of a speech culture of students during this period determines their social adaptation and future academic success.

In particular, the formation of a speech culture in primary grades is an urgent issue today. Working on the correctness of speech, improving the speech culture of primary school students is one of the main directions of the teacher's educational and methodological activities [5; p. 12].

The issue of forming a speech culture has long occupied a central place in the work of Eastern thinkers. Al-Farabi says the following about speaking correctly, drawing logical conclusions, and being a meaningful and beautiful speaker: "When we come to how to give and receive education, how to express and explain thoughts, how to ask and how to answer, I affirm that the first of these sciences is the science of language, which gives names to bodies, that is, substance (independent, self-existent) and accident (accidental manifestations).

The second science is grammar: it teaches how to arrange the names given to bodies and how to construct wise sayings and discourses that express the arrangement of substance and accident and the result that follows from them.

The third science is logic: it teaches how to arrange propositions according to logical figures in order to draw certain conclusions, by means of which we learn what we do not know and judge what is true and what is false" [2;p. 54].

METHODS. The term speech is derived from the Arabic word, which means speech, speech; the ability to speak. The use of language in the processes of expressing and exchanging thoughts; the process of using language tools by the speaker and the product of this process.

As is known, the place and role of speech and thinking in human life has long interested many people. Thinkers such as Al-Farabi, Zamakhshari, Al-Biruni, Ibn Sina, Yusuf Khos Hajib, Kaykovus, Alisher Navoi noted speech in their works as one of the signs of spiritual perfection.

In particular, Al-Farabi says the following about the power of speech: "...the power of speech (speech) is such a power that with its help a person acquires knowledge and skills, with the help of which he can distinguish between ugly and beautiful actions in his behavior and perform necessary and unnecessary actions, at the same time he understands what is harmful and useful, what is pleasant and what is bitter" [2; 188-p.]. M. Kashgari's work "Devon-u lug'otit turk" contains the proverb "The beginning of morality is language." This shows how our great ancestors emphasized the importance of language in the formation and development of human spirituality. Yusuf Khos Hajib says that human intelligence and knowledge are revealed through language and words, and calls for fluent speech: "Language is the interpreter and translator of intelligence and knowledge.

Enlightenment, goodness, and virtues come to a person through language, and this should be well understood. A person finds both honor and respect through language. ... Never speak too much. Speak too little. Write down a complex word with one word, that is, strive to imbue more meaning into a few words." Kaykovus in his work "Qobusnama" recognizes the culture of speech as follows: "... when speaking in front of the people, let your words be beautiful, let the people accept these words. Let the people know that you have reached a high level with your words, because they know a person's rank through words, ... everyone's situation is hidden under their words." [4]

The issue of developing the speech of primary school students is addressed in current methodological literature based on different approaches to knowledge about language, vocabulary, and speech culture.

The issue of developing students' speech in the process of teaching their native language was studied in the 30s-50s of the last century by A. Sa'diy, S. Dolimov; after the 60s by such scientists as Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences Y. Abdullaev, Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences Q. Abdullaeva, Professor K. Kasimova, B. Turdiev, A. Gulomov, M. Askarova, S. Matchonov, Sh. Yusupova, T. Ziyodova. A. Sa'diy noted the importance of oral and written descriptions of characters in teaching literature, and S. Dolimov noted the importance of written descriptions and students' speech in organizing literary creative works. In the methodological manual "Development of speech in the 1st grade" by Q. Abdullaeva, methods for teaching students to pronounce sounds and words correctly, independently organize logical exercises during literacy training, use didactic materials, and demonstration are described [1]. K. Kasimova in her book "Working on vocabulary in the 5th grade mother tongue lessons" discusses the methodology for organizing vocabulary exercises.[9] The vocabulary of the language creates great opportunities for the student's speech development to communicate with others. The teacher must teach students to use language units in different situations, to be conscious of their speech, and to feel responsible for each word they say. The mother tongue as a subject of study should not only help to master theoretical knowledge, but also to form the skills of practical application of language units that are necessary for a person throughout his life.

B. Turdiev's manual "Practical on the development of written speech" covers general theoretical issues of written speech, auxiliary written work, written work related to independent work on a book, filling out worksheets, teaching how to write statements and essays.

A. Gulomov, M. Qodirov's book "Methodology of speech development in Uzbek" gives the theoretical and practical importance of speech development, methodological recommendations for organizing exercises on speech development.

The manual "Development of speech in young children", created by a group of scientists under the leadership of M. Askarova, is mainly devoted to the study of issues of speech development in kindergarten children [3]. It is important to remember that developing the speech of preschool children is a foundation for subsequent stages of education, and that it is necessary to determine in advance the content of speech development classes, teaching methods, an individual approach to children, and the development of the speech activity of each child at all stages of the training.

The manual "Uzbek language teaching methodology" created by B. Tokhliev, M. Shamsieva, T. Ziyodova pays special attention to the methodology of developing students' speech and enriching their vocabulary in connection with grammatical topics in the preparation of future specialists for school education [6]. Various exercises that ensure the acquisition of knowledge on all subjects taught in primary school are aimed at developing students' skills in literate writing, correct pronunciation and oral speech, and enriching students' vocabulary is a prerequisite for mastering academic subjects and forming a culture of oral and written speech.

Sh. Yusupova in her monograph "Philosophical foundations of developing students' thinking in modern Uzbek literary language lessons" noted that the use of independent work types in native language education is effective in achieving practical language mastery by students [7]. Increasing students' cognitive activity, getting them interested in reading, and forming their skills for independent learning are urgent problems. It is known that, along with concepts such as cognitive activity, cognitive activity, and cognitive initiative, cognitive independence is also of great importance.

RESULTS. The grammatical knowledge and skills given to students in the primary grades, as well as the skills related to speech and spelling, are considered to be thoroughly mastered only if they are used not only in individual words and sentences, but also in logically thought-out examples presented in statements and essays. In order to form the skills of creating an independent text in a student, it is necessary to work first of all on developing his oral speech. Because the more developed the student's oral speech is, the more this is reflected in his written speech. In order for a student to describe an event, whether in writing or orally, he must have a certain level of vocabulary, be able to find words and word combinations that are appropriate to the content of the topic in order to clearly express his thoughts on a particular topic, and be able to use them in their place in speech.

The analysis of research has shown that speech knowledge and speech skills are two different phenomena. Speech knowledge is acquired on the basis of mastering knowledge of all levels of the language, while speech skills are the use of the speech system in various speech styles. During speech activity, a person pays attention not to words, but to the meaning of the word and chooses the right word to clearly express his thoughts. Speech skills are the ability to quickly adapt and plan the direction of speech, find language tools to develop the content of speech, and put them into practice.

K.D. Ushinsky noted that "the development of speech in children is almost the same as the development of logical thinking in them". Logical thinking is formed and develops in primary school, and continues to improve throughout life. Human thought is expressed in the forms and means of language. No matter how complex the content of thought is, it can be consistently reflected with the help of syntactic constructions and morphological forms of the language. Thus, mastering the language, having a sufficient vocabulary and grammatical forms creates the basis for the development of thinking.

E. Goziev emphasizes that reality is reflected with the help of speech, and speech is one of the important properties of the psychology of thinking.

Speech is a specific form of life as a separate type of social activity in the process of expressing and exchanging ideas, and it is understood as the processes of its oral and written manifestation, that is, the process of speaking, its result. In linguistic theory, the concept of speech is contrasted with the abstract concept of language, which is a system of means of expression adopted in a particular language community, and the specific, somewhat more general concept of language, which is one of the most characteristic manifestations of social existence. Written speech differs from oral speech in that it is somewhat more structured, words are selected very carefully, grammatically clear, but complex in structure, and cannot use the intonation, facial expressions, and hand gestures characteristic of oral speech.

DISCUSSION. There are monological and dialogical types of speech, depending on the field of application, such forms as artistic speech, scientific speech, official speech. In any form and in any case, clarity, fluency, simplicity, expressiveness should remain the most important features of speech [8; p. 425]. Well-developed speech serves as one of the important tools of human activity in society. For a student, speech is a tool for successful learning at school. In order to develop speech activity and student speech, it is necessary to pay attention to the following:

1. There must be a demand for the emergence of a person's speech.
2. Any speech must have content, material. The more complete, rich, valuable this material is, the more meaningful its presentation will be.
3. It is necessary to arm speech with language tools. It is necessary to give students language samples, create good speech conditions for them. As a result of hearing speech and using it in their own experience, children consciously form a "language perception".

There are a number of aspects of speech acquisition. These are:

1. Mastering the norms of the literary language. The school teaches students to distinguish literary language from simple colloquial language, dialect and jargon, introduces them to artistic, scientific, colloquial variants of the literary language.
2. Mastering important speech skills necessary for every member of our society, namely reading and writing skills. In this way, students learn the features of written speech, its difference from oral-colloquial speech.
3. Improving the speech culture of students. Language is the most important means of communication in society. Based on this social significance of language, special attention is paid to the speech culture of students at school [105; p. 300].

By the time children reach the age of six, they have mastered the most important means of morphology and many forms of syntax within the framework of the style of speech. In other words, children acquire their native language through speech activity, speech reception, and speaking. Therefore, it is very important to create conditions for children's speech activity, communication, and expression of their thoughts.

Determining the set of pedagogical conditions for the formation of speech culture skills in primary school students, we were guided by the requirements of modern society for the education of the native language, the content of language education for primary school students.

Pedagogical ideas about communication, its essence, significance and role in the educational process made it possible to note the following:

- a) communication in the history of domestic and foreign pedagogy is associated with a person's need for self-understanding, development of consciousness and manifestation of

independence (J. Dewey, I.G. Pestalossi, L.N. Tolstoy, K.D. Ushinsky, etc.);

b) communication is a situation of searching for the essence of values and strengthening them in experiences and actions (E.V. Bondarevskaya, Z.I. Vasilyeva, I.A. Kolesnikova, A.P. Tryapisyna, etc.);

c) communication - provides anthropocentrism, understanding and empathy, reveals the individuality of a person (R.Yu. Khudoyberganov, V. Diltey, Ye.I. Kazakova, A.G. Rivin, etc.);

d) upbringing with and within culture, on the one hand, ensures a person's natural entry into social life and communication, and on the other hand, it is through communication that the assimilation of cultures occurs (T.G. Braje, I.S. Gracheva, A.V. Mudrik, etc.).

Table 1.1. Content of the components of the formation of speech culture of primary school students

Component Content	Component Content
Linguistic • knowledge of active lexical, grammatical and phonetic material;	Linguistic • knowledge of active lexical, grammatical and phonetic material;
• knowledge of the graphic system of the language;	• knowledge of the graphic system of the language;
• spelling rules, their reliance on different principles;	• spelling rules, their reliance on different principles;

The content of the components of the formation of speech culture in primary school students allows us to conclude that the following are necessary when teaching students this type of speech activity: mastering language rules, learning to use them to express one's own or others' thoughts through the means of the native language, as well as mastering the skill of using various supports to independently construct one or another written thought. In this case, the teacher's task is to create favorable conditions for the successful implementation of all components in the educational process.

Successful mastery of written and oral speech, which allows for the formation of speech culture in primary school students, requires the formation of practical skills by performing special exercises, ensuring the combination of traditional and interactive methods.

The main task of primary school native language classes is to prepare students for educational activities, to form a person who can communicate with others, and to convey his thoughts to others in an understandable way.

The content of the subject "Mother Language" for the formation of personal speech culture in primary school students includes three components: linguistic, psychological and methodological.

CONCLUSION. The formation of speech culture in primary school students is not just a literacy lesson, but a strategic pedagogical process that determines the spiritual and intellectual future of the nation. The language of a child of primary school age is like soft wax that is just being formed; whatever shape it is given, the person will be formed in the future.

The results of our research clearly show that in order to successfully form a speech culture, it is necessary to transform the educational process from a dry set of rules into a lively, creative and

communicative field. The teacher's high speech example, innovative speech situations used in lessons, and the child's freedom of thought are the main pedagogical conditions for raising an excellent speaker. Raising a generation whose speech is beautiful, whose thoughts are deep, and who is proud of the rich possibilities of their native language is the highest and most undeniable goal of primary education.

REFERENCES

1. Abdullaeva, Q. *Speech Development in Grade 1*. Tashkent: Teacher Publishing House, 1968.
2. Abu Nasr al-Farabi. *The City of Virtuous People*. Tashkent: Abdulla Qodiriy National Heritage Publishing House, 1993, p. 188.
3. Asqarova, M., et al. *Developing Speech in Young Children*. Tashkent: Uzbekistan Publishing House, 2001.
4. Kaykovus. *Qabusnama*. Tashkent: New Century Generation Publishing House, 2016, 224 p.
5. Lvov, M. R. *The Speech of Younger Schoolchildren and Ways of Its Development*. Moscow, 1975, p. 12.
6. To'xliiev, B., Shamsieva, M., & Ziyodova, T. *Methodology of Teaching the Uzbek Language*. Tashkent, 2010.
7. Yusupova, Sh. *Philosophical Foundations for Developing Students' Thinking in Modern Uzbek Literary Language Classes*. Tashkent: Fan Publishing House, 2004.
8. *National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan*. Vol. 6. Tashkent: National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan Publishing House, 2003, 704 p., p. 425.
9. Qosimova, K., Matchonov, S., G'ulomova, X., Yo'ldosheva, Sh., & Sariev, Sh. *Methodology of Teaching the Mother Tongue*. Tashkent: Noshir Publishing House, 2009, 352 p.